

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Review Article on Recent Advances in The Pharmacological Diversification of Imidazole Derivatives

Dr. K. Chandra Sekhar M. S.*, K. Sravana Lakshmi

Dr. K.V. Subba Reddy Institute of Pharmacy, Dupadu, Kurnool.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 12 April, 2025

Keywords:

Heterocyclic compound,
Furan, Antifungal, Antiviral,
Antiulcer, Anticancer.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15205082

ABSTRACT

Furan a five membered aromatic heterocyclic ring system with O present at 1st position made up of 4C and 4 H atoms furan ring is a part of many natural products like Furano flavonoid, furanocoumarins, etc... Furan nucleus show several biological applications and also shows strong affinity for a range of receptors furan and its derivatives are used in synthesis of many novel drugs. The antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anti-depressant, anti-anxiolytic, anti-Parkinson, anti-glaucoma, muscle-relaxant, anti-hypertensive, diuretics, anti-ulcer, anti-aging, anti-cancer, anti-osteoporosis, anti-sickling activities of furan make them frequently utilized. Furan is a plane colourless fluid which is highly volatile and combustible in nature. This article aims to review about the biological activities of furan and its derivatives during past years.

INTRODUCTION

Cyclic ring systems with at least one hetero atom are called heterocycles. Atoms other than carbon atoms like Nitrogen(N), Oxygen(O), Sulphur(S) are some of the most frequently used hetero atoms. Heterocycles are found in almost all plants and animal products and are major constituents of almost half of the natural organic compounds alkaloids, natural dyes, proteins, enzymes, etc... are some of the examples of natural organic compounds. Hetero cycles have wide range of

applications in agrochemicals, veterinary, and pharmaceutical products these compounds are very important in daily life activity of humans beings starting from food to most complex cancer treatment drugs hormones, haemoglobin, vitamins, dyes and pigments, antibiotics, even most essential amino acids have heterocyclic structures in them. Heterocycles can be classified into different categories based on their electronic structures, presence of double bond based on presence of double bond they are classified as saturated compounds and unsaturated compounds.

***Corresponding Author:** Dr. K. Chandra Sekhar M. S.

Address: Dr. K.V. Subba Reddy Institute of Pharmacy, Dupadu, Kurnool.

Email ✉: chandrashekharkadaiahgari@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Saturated heterocycles include piperidine, oxetane, etc. behave like acyclic derivatives with modified steric properties and does not possess any double bonds. unsaturated compounds include furan, pyrrole; thiophene, pyridine, etc...and these compounds will have double bonds.[1]

Furan:

Fig-1Furan

Furan is a five membered aromatic heterocyclic ring system comes under the category of unsaturated heterocycles oxygen is the main hetero atom present in this heterocycle. Furan is a bioactive aromatic compound with numerous biological applications. 2-furoic acid was the first furan derivative found by Carl Wilhelm Scheufound in 1780.[2]

Physical Properties

Furan is highly volatile and combustible in nature it is a plane colourless liquid which can be boiled almost at ambient temperature and pressure range and has a boiling point of 32°C melting point of furan is -85.6°C and smells like chloroform. It dissolves in most organic solvents but relatively weakly soluble in water and highly soluble in organic solvents like acetone, alcohol, bran, ether.

Molecular weight: 68.07g/mol and a density of 0.936g/ml

Dipole moment: 0.72 Dybe [2]

Chemical properties of furan:

Furan has an oxygen moiety at 1st position with 2 lone pair of electrons. So, furan generally undergo electrophilic substitution reactions (at 2nd position) like nitration, halogenation, sulfonation etc... all these electrophilic reactions are only possible because of electron donating effect shown by oxygen [2]

Aromatic Nature of Furan:

Furan has a total of 6 π electrons and 32 protons. The electron:proton ratio of furan is 0.1875 (6:32)Furan is an electron rich compound it sources it's electrons from both carbon nuclei (4) and oxygen nuclei(2).

- π -Electrons:Furan has a planar ring structure with $(4n+2)\pi$ electrons where n can be any integer with a positive value(including 0) n=1 for furan.
- Planarity: The ring is planar allowing for effective overlap of p-orbitals
- Conjugation: Each atom in the ring has a p-orbital

This delocalisation of electrons across the ring provides furan with its aromatic stability.Aromaticity of furan helps in increasing the shelf life of the product any aromatic ring participate in π - π stacking interactions with DNA proteins and other biological targets such interactions can improve binding affinity between drug and target aromatic rings affects the electrons distribution between drug and target increase its potency and also increase metabolic stability of the drug all most all aromatic drugs have lipophilicity which helps in penetration of drugs into cell membranes , synergistic effect i.e aromatic compounds synergise with other drugs enhancing their efficacy (furan containing compounds will

enhance the efficacy of anti-bacterial activity of anti-biotics)[2]

Biological significance of furan and its derivatives:

Furan as Anti-bacterial agent:

This information has been extracted from the experiment done by Saeid H, Al-Sayeed-al...[20] 2,4-di substituted furans showed markable effects against the gram (+) bacteria than gram (-) ones these show their activity by cell wall destruction method the gram(+) bacteria has an cell wall which is made up of peptidoglycan layer which is ineffective and permeable to drug components whereas the gram (-) ones are made of

peptidoglycan and phospholipidic layer which is impermeable and furan or its derivatives show no action against it. The presence of methoxy, chloro and fluoro (more electro negative group) substituted on phenyl groups (aromatic ring connected to amid nitrogen) improve its activity against bacteria (+) like Streptococcus pyogenes, Proteus vulgaris and Escherichia coli.

Results:

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration :100µg/ml High activity was shown by 5-[(Benzene Sulfonyl-methyl-amino)-methyl]-furan-3-carboxylic acid-(2,6-dimethoxy-phenyl)-amide when Ampicillin is taken as standard. In vitro studies are done using agar well diffusion method.

Fig-2 Anti-Bacterial Activity of Furan

Biological Significance of Furan & its derivatives as Anti-Cancer Agent:

This experiment was conducted by Jarosław Widelski [21] A kind of malignant neoplasm where abnormal cell growth and cell division is triggered by various factors which may lead to malignant anaemia, organ rupture, etc.... eventually to death. Furocoumarin is a secondary metabolite synthesised against bacterial or fungal infections these are used in combination with ultra violet radiation therapy in treating mainly breast cancer.

Mechanism: Psoralen is a linear furanocoumarin it inhibits cell cycle and proliferation and cells are programmed to death (apoptosis or autophagy) these components basically act by inhibition of the activation of transcription factor NF κ B (nuclear factor kappa B) which is responsible for the converting polarised epithelial cells to mesenchymal cell and it also inhibits anti-apoptotic proteins (c-FLIP, FADD like 1L-1 β -converting enzymes) and activates pro-apoptotic polypeptides (n-terminal kinase) this helps in blocking of cell cycle at G1/S phase. Psoralen and

its derivatives reduce the count of cytoplasmic exosomes which are generally secreted out by the cell by reducing its count the amount of accumulation is also reduced and increase other cancer drug concentrations in blood plasma this phenomenon is also known as multidrug resistance (MDR) found by Dr Wang and his colleagues

Method of Analysis: Flow Cytometry

In this method we use HL60cell(cell line derived from peripheral blood) and PHA(phytohemagglutinin) stimulated PBLs(peripheral lymphocytes) to check the immunomodulating activity of Psoralen using fluorescent markers and taking cell size cell shape

as parameters. And unstimulated PBLs cells as control group

Results: The % inhibition of cell growth from G0 to G1 phase.

Table-4[21]

Time	Control group	Psoralen
24hrs(HL60 cells)	41.1 %	44.0%
24hrs(PBLs cells)	66.0 %	56.9%

Minimum Effective Concentration :80µg/ml

The presence of Methoxy groups(5-methoxypsoralen) showed maximum effect with least concentration(100µM)

Fig-3 Anti-Cancer Activity of Furan

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as an Anti-Inflammatory agent:

The information has been extracted from the experiment done by Marques RV, Sestito SE et al..[22] Inflammation is a basic reaction to any kind of infections or injury. Redness warmth, swelling & pain are absorbed as a response which activates the immune system to produce inflammatory mediators like Nitric oxide synthase, cellular cytokinin interleukins and prostaglandin, however prolonged inflammation may lead to autoimmune disorders, cancer, vascular disorders.

Mechanism: it involves down regulation of mitogen activated protein kinase and activator protein-1 activation.

Method used to analyse: Using RAW 264.7 murine macrophage cell culture (macrophage cell line obtained from tumour in male mouse) when induced with Abelson murine leukaemia virus) with different concentrations in the presence and absence of LPS (Lippo polysaccharide a pathogen associated molecular pathway) LPS induced inflammatory mediators were analysed by ELISA and real time PCR and modifications in the signalling pathway is analysed by western blotting

technique Danshen (Methoxy benzo(B) Furan) bioactive compound obtained from salvia miltiorrhiza a type of microbe

Results: 20 μ M is maximum effective concentration after this it may lead to neuro & hepatotoxicity it showed a decrease in levels of IL-1 β , IL-6, NO, PEG₂

Fig-4 Anti-Inflammatory activity of furan

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as anti- glaucoma agent:

This information has been extracted from the experiment done by Ayla Balaban, Gokhan Parlakgumus et-al...[23] Glaucoma is a condition with elevated intra ocular pressure(caused by increased aqueous humour levels) in the eye which may lead to optic nerve damage followed by vision impairment. Carbonic anhydrase enzyme responsible to produce aqueoushumourhelps to maintain the eye pressure by converting CO₂&water to bicarbonates and its products which influence fluid transport. 2-acetylfuranmethanesulfonylhydrazone, 5-nitro-2-furaldedehydemethanesulfonylhydrazone furansulfonyl hydrazone derivatives synthesised from hydrazine and sulfonic acid as primary reactants

Mechanism: These compounds competitively inhibit CA-1 (hydroxy carboxylic acid receptor - 1)decrease production of aqueous humour in the ciliary bodyof eye there by it decreases the IOP.

Methods used to analysis:

Spectrophotometric method used to analyse inhibitory effects of compounds using parameters like K_m, IC₅₀& K. Electro chemical method used to analyse redox behaviours of the compounds the peaks are determinedusing differential pulse voltameter

Results:5-nitro-2-furaldedehydemethanesulfonylhydrazone had shown moreinhibitory effect than the other due to the presence of NO₂ groupsbecause of its electron withdrawing nature which increased affinity with enzymes active sites with nearest activity to standard compound AAZ (acetazolamide).

Table-5[23]

Compound	K _m (M)	IC ₅₀ (M)	K _i (M)	Inhibition type
	25.30 $\times 10^{-5}$	1.02 $\times 10^{-4}$	5.88 $\times 10^{-6}$	Competitive

<p>N'-methylidenmethanesulfonohydrazide - 2-methyl-5-nitrofurán</p>				
<p>AAZ (acetazolamide)</p>	24.21×10^{-5}	1.12×10^{-3}	2.55×10^{-5}	Competitive

Fig-5,6 Anti-Glaucomactivity of Furan.

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as Anti-ulcer agent:

This information has been extracted from the experiment done by Mariano Ezequiel Vera, María Laura Mariani et-al... [24] Any destruction caused in the gut mucosal lining will lead to ulcer formation there are many factors which can trigger this condition some of them are Helicobacter pylori infections, anti-inflammatory drugs and imbalance in serotonin levels, excessive activation of mast cell (leads to excessive HCL) Derivatives of sesquiterpene lactones showed remarkable effects. (40mg/kg) Dehydroleucodine (obtained from Artemisia douglasiana), (40mg/kg) Xanthain (Xanthium cavanillesii Schouw), (40mg/kg) 3-benzoxymethyl-5H-furan-2-one (semi synthetic butanolide)

Mechanism: These lactones exhibit their mast cell stabilizing effect by inhibiting degranulation and serotonin release from human and murine (rat) mast cell and also block signalling pathway

downstream of cytosolic calcium increase it's a dose dependent mechanism

Methods used to analyse: 2 methods of evaluation is done lesion. Effect of 3 lactones Effect of 3 lactones on erosion

1. **Scoring system:** estimates efficiency through degree of erosion

2. **Light microscopy:** gives an estimation on no. of mast cells and degree of lesion

Carboxy methyl cellulose is taken as reference group (0.4%)

Results:

comparison between effect on ulcer both individually and in combination with 48/80 (a standard polymer decrease ulcer by degranulating mast cells) 48/80 also taken standard as control group all the lactones' groups showed same effect individually and in combination with 48/80 SEM (structural equation modelling p is

just its degree of indication)++ p<0.001 and for individually 48/80 SEM+++ p,0.001.

Serum serotonin concentrations:

The lactones SEM+++p<0.001 FOR 48\80 group SEM+p<0.005 it shows that the lactone groups has shown overall great anti- ulcer activity than the control and the 48/80 compound.

Fig-7 Anti-Ulcer Activity of Furan

Fig-8 Anti-Ulcer Activity of Furan

Fig-9 Anti-Ulcer Activity of Furan

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as Anti-Parkinsoniansagent:

This information has been extracted from the experiment done by. LeWitt PA, Aradi SD, Hauser et-al..[25] Parkinsons is a neurological disorder characterised by tremors, bradykinesia, rigidity, impaired coordination due to lot of reasons like age, loss of dopamine producing neurons (in substantia nigra part of brain) or Lewy bodies (abnormal protein lumps in brain). Preladenant is an adenosine receptor antagonist(A_{2A}) that improves motor functions it's obtained by modifying side chain of SCH-58261(10) which is currently under phase 2 clinical trials registered with no:NCT00406029

Mechanism: Adenosine (A_{2A}) receptors are generally responsible for brake on movement or stopping the motor activity by blocking its functions we can improve the motor function in parkinsonian patients. Preladenant acts as an antagonist to the receptor and reduce mean daily off time

Study design: according to block randomised schedule patients (234) were given 1mg,2mg,5mg,10mg or a placebo. Efficacy analysis:234 Patients (189 Preladenant,45 placebo)

Efficacy results: mean daily off is the major parameter considered here which means how effectively the medication managing the symptoms for a longer period of time 5mg Preladenant: reduced mean daily off time by 1hr compared to placebo(95%CI(Confidance Index)2.1to0 p(probability of observed results)=0.0486 10mg preladenant: reduced mean daily off time by 1.2 hr compared to placebo (95% CI:2.2to0.2;p=0.019) Both 1mg &2mg didn't show any significant effect mean daily off time is also low 1mg(0.2hr), 2mg(-0.7hr)

Side effects:

Table-6[25]

Name Side Effect	Preladenant	Placebo
Somnolence	10%	6%
Dyskinesia	9%	13%
Insomnia	5%	9%

Results: 5mg and 10mg showed significant result and significantly reduced off time in patients.

Fig-10Anti-Parkinson activity of furan

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as Muscle relaxant & Anti-hypertensive agent:

This information has been extracted from the experiment conducted by Irma Martinsen, Vilma Zigmantaitet-al...[26] In a recent invitro study on male Wistarratsshowed anti -hypertensive and muscle relaxant propertiesof essential oil which has been extracted from the Elsholtzia Ciliata. it showed a concentration dependent reduction in phenylephrine induced contraction in both prostate and aorta. The main constituents of this essential oil are 2-acetyl furan (2AF) and 5-methyl furan(5-AF)Dehydroelsholtzia ketone(86.23%), Elsholtzia ketone (10.64%)

Mechanism: they show these activities by blocking α -adrenergic receptors mostly of α_{1A} & α_{1D} subtypesit also showed inhibitory effects on Na^+ and Ca^{2+} current this effect is mediated by inhibition of L-type calcium channels

Method of analysis: They used Tension measurement as a parameter in this we record the force generated by the aortic rings and ventral prostrate strips when they contract Resting tension: the tissues initially stretched to a specific resting tension for aortic rings is 1.5g and for prostrate strip is 1g to stimulate one contraction or to stimulate physiological conditions

Results: n represents no.of experiments conducted

Table-7[26]

Values	Prostrate	Aortic rings
IC ₅₀	0.24±0.03μL/ml(n=10)	0.72 0.11(n=4)

EC₅₀ values of phenylephrine is 0.18 0.13 (n=5)

EC₅₀ values of 2AF is 0.81 0.3 (n=5)

EC₅₀ values of 5MF is 0.69 0.23 (n=5)

SEM p<0.005

The essential oil showed significant efforts as anti-hypertensive agent and smooth muscle relaxant on both aortic rings and prostrate strips.

Fig-11,12 Muscle relaxant & anti-hypertensive activity of furan

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as Anti-Microbial agent:

The information has been extracted from the experiment done by Piotr Iwanowski, Ashima Bhatia et-al..[27]

Antibiotic resistance is the major concern in the pharmaceutical field resistance it can be developed by many reasons due to misuse of antibiotics etc... One of such cases is Macrolide resistant to Pneumonia harbouring penicillin resistant isolates in community -acquired pneumonia in adults.

Nafithromycin(WCK4873)(96) is a semi synthetic antibiotic derived from kitasamycin a natural macrolide produced by a bacterium called Streptomyces kitasatoensis

Mechanism:

Though nafithromycin classified as a ketolide it has an additional lactone ring instead of carbon moiety. This plays an important role in inhibiting RNA-dependent protein biosynthesis and enables nafithromycin to show potent activity against macrolide-resistant Pneumonia, methicillin-susceptible *S.aureus* 21ATCC29213 *E.faecalis* ATCC29211, *S.pyogenes*, *H.influenza*.

Methods used to analyse:

Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics were tested using randomised double blind placebo-controlled studies (clinical trials no: NCT03979859)

Single Ascending Dose study:

Dose: 100 to 1200mg

Conditions: Administered under fasted and fed conditions

Findings: Nafithromycin was well tolerated at all dose levels recorded no deaths and emergency

adverse conditions the study didn't show any significant difference in tolerability between fed and fasted conditions.

Multiple Ascending Dose Study:

Doses: 600,800&1000mg administered once daily for 7 days under fed conditions

Findings: Nafithromycin was well tolerated at all doses no serious ADRS recorded.

Results:

Single Dose Study:

Highest plasma concentrations were observed between 1 and 6 hours post dose. Maximum plasma concentration ranged from 0.099 to 1.742 mg/L Plasma exposure increased more than dose proportionally and was influenced by food intake

Multiple dose study:

On 7 days, highest plasma concentration (1.340 to 2.987mg/L) AUC₀₋₂₄ ranged from 13.48 to 43.46hmg/L Steady state was achieved after 3 days for 600&800 mg doses and after 4 days for 1000mg dose.

Fig-15 Anti-Microbial Activity Of Furan

(3R,3aS,4R,6R,8R,9R,10R,12R,15R)-9-[[[(2S,3R,4S,6R)-4-(Diméthylamino)-3-hydroxy-6-méthyltétrahydro-2H-pyran-2-yl]oxy]-15-éthyl-8-méthoxy-4,6,8,10,12,15a-hexaméthyl-2,5,11,13-tétraoxo-N'-(1S)-1-[5-(2-pyridinyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl]éthoxy]tétradécahydro-2H-furo[2,3-c]oxacyclotétradécine-3-carboximidamide (Nafithromycin).

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as Anti-Sickling agent:

This information has been extracted from the experiment done by Pak Hin Chow Charles D et al..[28] Sickle cell anaemia is a pathological disorder related to RBC. Shape of RBC is

generally biconcave which has a larger surface area but in this condition the patients RBC will change their shape into a sickle-like structure which reduces surface area and O₂ carrying capacity of cell there may be many causes for this condition like genetic mutations, dehydration, decrease in haemoglobin level. 5-HMF(5-hydroxymethyl furfural), 5-PMFC(5-(phoxymethyl)furan2-carbaldehyde) are obtained as by products from Maillard reaction in which we use sweet potato and other sugar containing food to obtain it. It can be extracted by dehydration of carbohydrates such as fructose, glucose etc. under acidic conditions. It is currently under phase-2 clinical trials (NCT01737814)

Mechanism: Under hypoxic conditions RBC activate a cation(aquaporin) leak which may lead to cellular dehydration and sickle cell formation. Aquaporin-1 is a water channel present in blood cells which maintains water homeostasis and cell structure 5-HMF and its derivatives act by blocking AQP-1 ION channel and inhibiting its leakage (conductance) which decreases chances of haemolysis and sickle cell formation.

Methods used to analyse: To know about efficacies of different products

Electrophysiology: in this method we record voltage between two electrodes in both non-AQP-1 controlled and AQP-1 expressing oocytes

Quantitative swelling assay: In this method swelling rate is measured the oocytes are kept in 50% hypotonic saline and cross-sectional area of the oocytes are measured.

Results:

5-PMFC is the most potent inhibitor of AQP-1 ion conductance (98% blocking rate at 100 μ M) When AQP-1 ion channel blocker (80 μ M) given along with a selective haemoglobin modifying agent 5-NMFC (2.5 mM) showed increased effectiveness to anti-sickling property in red blood cells of humans suffering with sickle cell anaemia. RBC has another non selective cation channel known as piezo-1 is also not affected by 5-HMF [at 2.55 mM]

Fig-16 Anti-sickling agent of furan

Fig-17 Anti-Sickling Agent of Furan

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as Anti-analgesic agent:

This information has been extracted from the experiment done by Sergei N. Igidov, Irina A. Gorbunova et-al. [28] Anti-analgesic activity of drugs helps in pain management in patients suffering from chronic pain, post-surgical pain, and pain from injuries even used in treatment of arthritis, neuropathic pain. 5-aryl-1-(furan-2-carbonyl)-1H-pyrazole-3-carboxylates by decyclization reaction the obtained product was analysed by NMR & IR spectroscopy

Mechanism: Neurons present in the peripheral somatosensory system which includes sensory nerve endings known as nociceptors which has the

capacity to detect pain and produce a neurotransmitter (prostaglandin) in response which increase the sensation of pain. The compound we took act by blocking the cyclooxygenase (COX-1) enzyme which is responsible for the synthesis of prostaglandins.

Method used for analysis: Hot plate method is used for the analysis the compound to be analysed is given as an intraperitoneal injection for both sexes of mice here the length of time mice stayed

on the hot plate without any signs of defensive pain reflex acts as an indicator to change in pain sensitivity. Every compound is tested on 6 animals Here we used Metamizole sodium injection with a dose of 93mg/kg (ED50)has been used as a standard. Latent period is the time taken for the onset of defensive reflex from the start maximum latent period was 40 s but in the experiment animals with latent period of not more than 15 seconds were used.

Results: Table-8[28]

Compound	Dosage (Mg/Kg)	Latent Period of Defensive Reflex (120min), S
N'-[5-(4-Methylphenyl)-2-oxofuran-3(2H)-ylidene]furan-2-carbohydrazide (4b)	50	26.60±1.36
N'-(2-Oxo-5-phenylfuran-3(2H)-ylidene)furan-2-carbohydrazide (4a)	50	24.80±0.97
Metamizole sodium	93 (ED50)	16.60±1.00

From the above table we can say that compounds 4b had shown highest analgesic activity.

Fig-18 Anti-Analgesic Activity of Furan

Fig-19 Anti-Analgesic Activity of Furan

Fig-20 Metamizole Sodium

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as Anti-Depressant & Anti-Anxiety agents:

The information has been extracted from the experiment done by Jagdish Kumar, Gita Chawla et-al.. [29] These central nervous system disorders occur due to various physiological and sociological factors. The pathophysiology of depression is not clearly known but decrease in concentrations of monoamines such as dopamine, serotonin and norepinephrine lead to these conditions. 3-(furan-2-yl)-5-(substituted phenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1,2-oxazole derivatives are obtained by a condensation reaction known as Claisen Schmidt different types of aromatic aldehydes are also used which further undergo cyclisation reaction to form products

Mechanism: The compound acts by stopping the metabolism of monoamines by inhibiting an enzyme called monoamine oxidase. It also binds with falcipain-2 receptor stops the receptor activity by occupying its active site by forming a hydrogen bond with it. Which decreases oxidative stress and therefore it also decreases anxiety and depression.

Methods used to analyse:

For Depression: (Forced swim Test)

Albino mice of 20 to 25 g they are injected with synthesised compound injected intraperitoneally

(10 mg/kg) and placed into a small cylinder containing water with fixed volume for 6 mins in the span of 6 mins we only record the duration of immobility (after 2 mins of struggle the rats are immobile and only moments required to keep their head float was observed (last 4 min) After 24 hrs imipramine reference drug is injected to same mice and 5 mins swim cycle is conducted and results are noted

For Anxiety: (Elevated plus maze method)

Mice were divided into different groups injected with diazepam (2 mg/kg) and test compounds 2 ml/kg intraperitoneally given. No. of entries towards open arms and closed arms and time of stay was recorded

Docking Studies

Glide module of Schrodinger-9 software is used to perform the experiment using protein preparation wizard method & root mean square deviation < 303D structure of falcipain-2 receptor is prepared using proper protonation and ioniser subprogramme at pH 7.2±0.2 energy minimised /cleaned up and Glide XP used for final docking studies.

Results: (4-[3-(Furan-2-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1,2-oxazol-5-yl]phenol) has the best anti-depressant activity with immobility

time 153.16 ± 0.30 **change from control -7.46
 MAO inhibition 47.33 ± 0.49 Neurotoxicity
 62.00 ± 0.57

Anti-anxiety activity: 15.86 preference to open arm and with an average time spent at the open arm 46.00 ± 0.57 **With neurotoxicity as 62.00 ± 0 .

Fig-21 Anti -Depressant& Analgesic Activity of Furan

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as Anti-Cholinesterase& Anti-Alzheimer agent:

This information has been extracted from the experiment done by Sadaf Saeed, Ameer Fawad Zahoor et-al..[30] Alzheimer`s is a neurological disorder characterised with symptoms like progressive memory loss, behavioural abnormalities, disorientation, decline in speech. It mainly occurs when there is an imbalance between the levels of acetyl cholinesterase (Ach) neurotransmitter. Ach increases memory encoding

capacity by making cortical circuits respond to sensory stimuli. Benzofuran thiazole derivatives are biproducts of hydrazinolysis of ester-4 with hydrazine monohydrate followed by cyclocondensation.

Mechanism: Benzo furo thiazole derivatives block the entrance of active site present in the acetylcholinesterase which blocks the entry of acetyl choline these benzo furo derivatives restricts the swinging gate present in the enzyme which is important for the entry of substrate and release of product these compounds enter the catalytic triad (a set of 3 amino acid residues that work together in the active site) of AchE and stop the enzymatic activity.

Methods used to analyse:

Ellman`s Method:

It`s is a spectrophotometric method in which the quantity of sulfhydryl groups are measured Ach catalyses the acetyl choline to produce thiocholine and acetate thiocholine and acetate thiocholine reacts with the Ellman reagent from yellow colour which is measured at 412nm.

Results:

10d shown highest inhibition activity due the presence of phenyl ring of acetamide and triazole when eserine taken as reference compound

Table-9[30]

Compound	Inhibition%(0.5mM)	IC ₅₀ (µM)
5-bromobenzofuran-triazoles derivative	81.45 ± 0.50	0.55 ± 1.00
Eserine	93.20 ± 1.15	0.06 ± 0.01

Fig-22 Eserine

Fig-23 Anti-Cholinesterase & Ant-Alzheimer's Activity O Furan

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as Anti-osteoporosis agent:

Si-tu Xue, Lei Zhang et-al.. did this experiment. et-al. [31] Our skeletal system generally consists of 2 types of cells osteoclast(bone breaking) and osteoblast(bone making)when heavy loss of bone occurs due to osteoclast cell activity or other factors may lead to osteoporosis. N-(2-(dimethylamine) ethyl)-6-methoxy benzofuran-2-carboxamide (125 compound) a benzofuran derivative this is used as a novel drug.

Mechanism: BMP-2(Bone Morphogenetic Protein) transcription pathway. BMP-2 is a protein which phosphorylates SMADs (proteins these activate Runx-2(runt-related transcription factor) protein through transcription induce cell differentiation and cell growth of osteoblast in bones Benzofurans show their action by

upregulating BMP-2 protein and help reduce resorption.

Method of analysis:

Dexamethasone treated zebra fish model

In this model induce dexamethasone into tibia bone with various concentrations like 1,5,25,100µM And the untreated fish is taken as reference group. Bone resorption is observed and equal ratios of 125 compound is also given using integrated optical density the bone is measured in both

Effect of Runx-2 transcription in invitro:

Lovastatin is taken as reference compound at different concentration its upregulation of proteins is compared with 125 group analysed by blotting techniques using protein samples.

Results:

In dexamethasone treated fish model 25µM of 125 completely offset the dexamethasone effect and reversed the resorption. In effect of Runax-2 transcription assay was performed and gave a comparison between upregulation activity of the protein factor table-10[30]

	Lovastatin	125compound
Concentration	10µM	100µM
% of upregulation at that conc.	255.6%	267.2%

Fig-24 Anti-osteoporosis activity of furan

Biological significance of furan & its derivatives as Anti-convulsant agents:

This information has been extracted from the experiment done by Khan SA, Naim MJ, Akhtar MJ. et-al...[32] Convulsions are involuntary muscle contraction of body experienced by people suffering with epilepsy, brain trauma (injuries to brain) people suffering with infections which affect brain. 1-(4-(2-(4-chlorobenzoyl)benzofuran-3-ylamino)-4-oxo butyl)pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid (8b) 1-(3-(2-(4-chlorobenzoyl)benzofuran-3-ylamino)-3-oxo propyl)pyrrolidine-2-carboxylic acid (7b) are analysed using NMR spectroscopy.

Mechanism:

MES model (Maximal Electroshock Seizure) in this method compounds act by inhibiting voltage-gated sodium channels which decrease the neuronal excitation and prevent conclusions. Sc MET model (subcutaneous Metrazol) in this method compounds act inhibiting GABA a g-protein couple receptor responsible for the excitation of neurons.

Method of analysis:

MES test:

60HZ alternating current of 50mA is induced for 0.2 sec and different concentrations 30,100,300mg/kg of compound 7b and 8b are also administered through ip every 1hr interval

Sc MET test:

It was mainly performed by to know about neurotoxicity Metrazol induce seizures (50mg/kg) different concentrations 30,100,300mg/kg of compound 7b and 8b are also administered through ip every 1hr interval.

Results:

MES test:

Effective median dose (ED₅₀) 7b-56.7mg/kg dose (ED₅₀)-8b-36.1mg/kg scMET test: compounds did not show any significant neurotoxic effects at 300mg/kg 7b-(100mg/kg, 0.5h;300mg/kg) 8b-(100mg/kg 0.5h and 4h) showed maximum anti-convulsive effect.

Fig-25 Anti-convulsant activity of furan

Fig-26 Anti-convulsant activity of furan

CONCLUSION:

The reviewed compounds of furan and its derivatives had shown affinity towards wide range of biological activities their biological and therapeutical values has been given by wide range of researchers and scientists. many significant activities like antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anti-depressant, anti-anxiolytic, anti-Parkinson, anti-glaucoma, muscle-relaxant, anti-hypertensive, diuretics, anti-ulcer, anti-aging, anti-cancer, anti-osteoporosis, anti-sickling activities have been showed by furan and its derivatives. In recent years the pharmaceuticals containing furan nucleus are rapidly growing and becoming very important in class or therapeutic agents they are likely to replace existing drugs in market due to their low toxicity and high efficacy many novel drug delivery systems are also being formulated using furan moiety drugs. these drugs show promising results in treat of many medical conditions and show a promising progress with regard to order compounds.

REFERENCES

1. Kabir E, Uzzaman M. A review on biological and medicinal impact of heterocyclic

compounds. Results in Chemistry. 2022 Jan 1;4:100606.

2. Nivrutti GP. Furan: A Promising Scaffold for Biological Activity.
3. Stiller CO, Hjemdahl P. Lessons from 20 years with COX-2 inhibitors: Importance of dose-response considerations and fair play in comparative trials. *Journal of Internal Medicine*. 2022 Oct;292(4):557-74.
4. Fadel C, Giorgi M. Synopsis of the pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, applications, and safety of firocoxib in horses. *Veterinary and Animal Science*. 2023 Mar 1;19:100286.
5. Loh GO, Wong EY, Tan YT, Ong LM, Ng RS, Wee HC, Peh KK. Simple and fast LC-MS/MS method for quantification of terazosin in human plasma and application to bioequivalence study. *Journal of Chromatography B*. 2021 Jan 15;1163:122517
6. Reist C, Streja E, Tang CC, Shapiro B, Mintz J, Hollifield M. Prazosin for treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *CNS spectrums*. 2021 Aug;26(4):338-44.
7. Kapourani A, Kontogiannopoulos KN, Barmplexis P. A review on the role of pilocarpine on the management of xerostomia

- and the importance of the topical administration systems development. *Pharmaceuticals*. 2022 Jun 18;15(6):762.
8. Dos Santos C, Dos Santos LS, Franco OL. Fosfomycin and nitrofurantoin: classic antibiotics and perspectives. *The Journal of Antibiotics*. 2021 Sep;74(9):547-58.
 9. Yang G, Ding S, Zhang J, Gu L, Zhai W, Kong C. Research progress on metabolites of nitrofurazone in aquatic products. *Heliyon*. 2024 Apr 16.
 10. McCarrell JL, Bailey TA, Duncan NA, Covington LP, Clifford KM, Hall 2nd RG, Blaszczyk AT. A review of citalopram dose restrictions in the treatment of neuropsychiatric disorders in older adults. *Mental Health Clinician*. 2019 Jul 1;9(4):280-6.
 11. Johansson S, Read J, Oliver S, Steinberg M, Li Y, Lisbon E, Mathews D, Leese PT, Martin P. Pharmacokinetic evaluations of the co-administrations of vandetanib and metformin, digoxin, midazolam, omeprazole or ranitidine. *Clinical pharmacokinetics*. 2014 Sep;53:837-47.
 12. Hughes AN, Li X, Lehman JS, Nelson SA, DiCaudo DJ, Mudappathi R, Hwang A, Kechter J, Pittelkow MR, Mangold AR, Sekulic A. Drug Repurposing Using Molecular Network Analysis Identifies Jak as Targetable Driver in Necrobiosis Lipoidica. *JID Innovations*. 2024 Nov 1;4(6):100296.
 13. Shing RH, Clayton LB, Smith SL, Watson MJ, McKenzie LM, Chalmers DP, Whitaker G, Bilmen JG. The novel rapid formulation of intravenous dantrolene (NPJ5008) versus standard dantrolene (Dantrium®): A clinical part-randomised phase 1 study in healthy volunteers. *European Journal of Anaesthesiology | EJA*. 2024 May 1;41(5):381-90.
 14. Ebrahim I, Maartens G, Wiesner L, Orrell C, Smythe W, McIlleron H. Pharmacokinetic profile and safety of adjusted doses of darunavir/ritonavir with rifampicin in people living with HIV. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*. 2020 Apr;75(4):1019-25.
 15. Cash TP, Alcalá S, Rico-Ferreira MD, Hernández-Encinas E, García J, Albarrán MI, Valle S, Muñoz J, Martínez-González S, Blanco-Aparicio C, Pastor J. Induction of lysosome membrane permeabilization as a therapeutic strategy to target pancreatic cancer stem cells. *Cancers*. 2020 Jul 4;12(7):1790.
 16. Rose R, Mitchell E, Van Der Graaf P, Takaichi D, Hosogi J, Geerts H. A quantitative systems pharmacology model for simulating OFF-Time in augmentation trials for Parkinson's disease: application to preladenant. *Journal of Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics*. 2022 Dec;49(6):593-606.
 17. Joshi AS, Shah RK, Suthar MH, Keharia UH. Evaluation of rationality of antimicrobial and antidiarrheal fixed dose combination available in Indian market. *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 2021;11(2):222-6.
 18. Saeid H, Al-sayed H, Bader M. A review on biological and medicinal significance of furan. *AlQalam Journal of Medical and Applied Sciences*. 2023 Feb 18:44-58.
 19. Sumorek-Wiadro J, Zając A, Maciejczyk A, Jakubowicz-Gil J. Furanocoumarins in anticancer therapy—For and against. *Fitoterapia*. 2020 Apr 1;142:104492.
 20. Marques RV, Sestito SE, Bourgaud F, Miguel S, Cailotto F, Reboul P, Jouzeau JY, Rahuel-Clermont S, Boschi-Muller S, Simonsen HT, Moulin D. Anti-inflammatory activity of bryophytes extracts in LPS-stimulated RAW264. 7 murine macrophages. *Molecules*. 2022 Mar 17;27(6):1940.

21. Gündüzalp AB, Parlakgümüş G, Uzun D, Özmen ÜÖ, Özbek N, Sarı M, Tunç T. Carbonic anhydrase inhibitors: Synthesis, characterization and inhibition activities of furan sulfonylhydrazones against carbonic anhydrase I (hCA I). *Journal of Molecular Structure*. 2016 Feb 5;1105:332-40.
22. Vera ME, Mariani ML, Aguilera C, Penissi AB. Effect of a Cytoprotective Dose of Dehydroleucodine, Xanthatin, and 3-Benzyloxymethyl-5 H-furan-2-one on Gastric Mucosal Lesions Induced by Mast Cell Activation. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2021 Jun 1;22(11):5983. LeWitt PA, Aradi SD, Hauser RA, Rascol O. The challenge of developing adenosine A2A antagonists for Parkinson disease: Istradefylline, preladenant, and tozadenant. *Parkinsonism & Related Disorders*. 2020 Nov 1;80:S54-63.
23. LeWitt PA, Aradi SD, Hauser RA, Rascol O. The challenge of developing adenosine A2A antagonists for Parkinson disease: Istradefylline, preladenant, and tozadenant. *Parkinsonism & Related Disorders*. 2020 Nov 1;80:S54-63.
24. Martišienė I, Zigmantaitė V, Pudžiuvytė L, Bernatoniene J, Jurevičius J. Elsholtzia ciliata Essential Oil Exhibits a Smooth Muscle Relaxant Effect. *Pharmaceuticals*. 2023 Oct 15;16(10):1464.
25. Mazur M, Masłowiec D. Antimicrobial activity of lactones. *Antibiotics*. 2022 Sep 29;11(10):1327.
26. Chow PH, Cox CD, Pei JV, Anabaraonye N, Nourmohammadi S, Henderson SW, Martinac B, Abdulmalik O, Yool AJ. Inhibition of the aquaporin-1 cation conductance by selected furan compounds reduces red blood cell sickling. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2022 Jan 17;12:794791.
27. Igidov SN, Gorbunova IA, Turyshev AY, Shipilovskikh DA, Kozlov DA, Rogova AS, Makhmudov RR, Silaichev PS, Igidov NM. Synthesis, recyclization under the action of methanol and analgetic activity of N'-(5-aryl-2-oxofuran-3 (2 H)-ylidene) furan-2-carbohydrazides. *Chimica Techno Acta*. 2023;10(1):202310101.
28. Kumar J, Chawla G, Gupta H, Akhtar M, Tanwar OP, Bhowmik M. Synthesis and neuropharmacological evaluation of some new isoxazoline derivatives as antidepressant and anti-anxiety agents. *Afr. J. Pharm. Pharmacol*. 2013;7(22):1523-30.
29. Saeed S, Zahoor AF, Kamal S, Raza Z, Bhat MA. Unfolding the antibacterial activity and acetylcholinesterase inhibition potential of benzofuran-triazole hybrids: Synthesis, antibacterial, acetylcholinesterase inhibition, and molecular docking studies. *Molecules*. 2023 Aug 10;28(16):6007
30. Xue ST, Zhang L, Xie ZS, Jin J, Guo HF, Yi H, Liu ZY, Li ZR. Substituted benzothiophene and benzofuran derivatives as a novel class of bone morphogenetic Protein-2 upregulators: Synthesis, anti-osteoporosis efficacies in ovariectomized rats and a zebrafish model, and ADME properties. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 2020 Aug 15;200:112465.
31. Pal R, Singh K, Paul J, Khan SA, Naim MJ, Akhtar MJ. Overview of chemistry and therapeutic potential of non-nitrogen heterocyclics as anticonvulsant agents. *Current Neuropharmacology*. 2022 Aug 1;20(8):1519-53.

HOW TO CITE: Dr. K. Chandra Sekhar M. S.*, K. Sravana Lakshmi, A Review Article on Recent Advances in The Pharmacological Diversification of Imidazole Derivatives, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 4, 1581-1599 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15205082>

